

scientific biography, lucidly written 'somewhat at the level of *Scientific American*', including some technicalities meant for the specialists. There are copious quotes and notes included, which have enriched the book immensely.

On the other hand, Wali has stated that his book *CHANDRA* 'is not intended to be an appraisal of Chandra's scientific work, nor is it a scientific biography'. One may apply to this biography of Rao the words of Wali that 'it may be perceived as merely laudatory, more like a memorial to a living person than a biography'. One would like to see a personality 'presented as a living figure with all his human traits and faults, which every man possesses, however great his genius'. In this context, Wali has quoted what Kapitsa had said referring to Rutherford: 'I see that time has absorbed all his minor human imperfections and I can only see a great man with an astounding brain and great human qualities'. So shall be foibles of Rao, which are not mentioned by Sundara Rajan.

The biography under review is very readable and flows smoothly, annotated with quotes from many of Rao's colleagues, friends and well-wishers from all over India and abroad. There are a few minor corrections to be taken care of. Apart from that, the only lacuna is perhaps the omission of an Index. The book is not to be construed as a scientific biography, as it would be a formidable task to put together such a work based on a bibliography that has to take into account more than a thousand publications in national and international journals. The book under review has to be read by the young in their formative years for it gives an inkling to the joy of science, the grit and determination that goes to the making of a scientist and if one may say so, a blueprint for success in one's scientific career. I am reminded of an other book, *Advice to a Young Scientist* by P. B. Medawar, which is pedagogical. On the other hand, here is a book that provides the life story of one who serves as a model scientist, a science

administrator and a teacher – all rolled into one.

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Communicating in Style. Yateendra Joshi. The Energy Resources Institute, New Delhi. 2003. 250 pp. Rs 300.

In a recent interview to *The Scientist*, sociobiologist and well-known author E. O. Wilson said that writing is more difficult than doing research. Many Indian scientists will agree with him.

This book is meant to help researchers, academics, journalists and managers whose work involves writing project reports, research papers, conference presentations, newsletters, manuals, posters, web pages, etc. present their material in a simple and straightforward manner so that their readers can get the message without much strain.

The book started as an in-house manual on writing. The author has consulted many established style guides and made comprehensive searches of the World Wide Web. Several drafts were field-tested before TERI decided to offer Joshi's style guide to a wider audience.

While it may not match the *Chicago Style Manual* in sheer size and depth of coverage, or the cute little classic *The Elements of Style* by William Strunk Jr. in its canonical status, or the more recent punctuation guide *Eats Shoots & Leaves* by Lynne Truss in the number of copies sold, the TERI style guide is most welcome for it is written with Indian users in mind. It is full of practical wisdom. I

recommend this book to researchers and doctoral students, especially those whose English language training is inadequate – which means about 90% of Indian scientists and students, thanks to the overall deterioration in standards of teaching English in our schools and colleges. Increasing use of 'e-malese' and SMS messages on cell phones have an evil influence over the way we use language. In addition, given its foreign origin, in the current political climate, English may be looked down upon.

The book is organized well and Joshi has covered virtually every aspect of writing, editing and publishing that an author needs to know. The 13 chapters cover not only the basic elements of style, choosing titles (headings), nuances of grammar, abbreviations and acronyms, punctuation, capitalization, preparation of tables, figures and lists, and quoting work by others, but also writing letters, faxes and e-mails, making effective presentations, designing quality posters, and submitting papers to journals. The annexes cover different formats of giving references in scholarly work, spellings and dictionaries, typography, and the right way to present postal and e-mail addresses and telephone numbers. Throughout the book the author's text is on the right-hand side pages and all examples, excerpts from the literature and useful sources of information are given on the left-hand side pages.

Researchers and research students will find this book valuable as a source of ready reference.

In a future edition Joshi might want to write about the use of a thesaurus and alert his readers to the excellent style guide of *The Economist* and the outstanding book, *Words into Print* by Marjorie E. Skillin and Robert M. Gray.

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